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Plant Biostimulants & their role in mitigating abiotic stress

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The different abiotic factors like soil composition, salinity level, soil pH, temperature fluctuations, water deficiency, pollution, moisture content in air, rain, wind or ultraviolet radiation effects both the quality and quantity of plant yield. This is because of the plant response to fight stress instead of focussing on yielding. Novel innovations are done by biotechnology to enhance the plant characteristics towards such stress conditions. Plant biostimulants (PBs) appears as a eco-friendly, sustainable and innovative way in enhancing tolerance to abiotic stresses and along with this elevating the quality of agricultural and horticultural crops. Plant biostimulants can be categorised into microbial and non-microbial biostimulants on the basis of their preparation source. Microbial biostimulants includes VAM fungi and soil bacteria having synergistic association with plants whereas non-microbial biostimulants includes organic (botanicals & seaweed extract from algae, terrestrial plants; protein hydrolysates, chitosan, humic & fulvic acids) and inorganic(silica & cobalt)substances. These can be used in the form of powder, granules, solution, foliar spray. Generally humic and nitrogenous biostimulants are mixed in soil directly while botanicals & seaweed derived biostimulants are used as spray over leaves. PBs can also be applied through water channel to plant rhizosphere for fast uptake. Biostimulants reduce abiotic stress in plants by interacting with various physio-chemical processes such as (i) reduced membrane lipid peroxidation, (ii) increased chlorophyll level (iii) improved antioxidant activities and (iv) an improved afflux and channelizing the intracellular ions. The prime objective of this review is to understand the role of plant biostimulants in mitigating the abiotic stress.

Keywords: abiotic, microbial, plant biostimulants, rhizosphere.